

Synthesis, structure, spectra and solution behavior of the nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of 3,7,10,14,15,19,20,24-octaazatricyclo[7.5.5.5^{2,8}]tetracosane (OCTC)

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Abstract : Synthesis of nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of three-dimensional tricyclic aza macrocycle 3,7,10,14,15,19,20,24-octaazatricyclo[7.5.5.5^{2,8}]tetracosane (OCTC) have been described. Metal-free ligand hydrochloride has also been prepared. Di- and tetrametallic complexes $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{OCTC} \cdot 8\text{HCl}$ have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductivity measurements and spectral studies. The thermodynamic stabilities of the complexes, investigated by pH-titration method, are low ($10^{17.78}$ and $10^{9.28}$, respectively) for the reactions $\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuA}^{2+}$ and $\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{NiA}^{2+}$ (A = OCTC) as expected to a non-planar [14]-N₄ ring. Further, structural rearrangement in Ni_2A^{4+} leads to coordination of each nickel(II) ion in different non-planar [12]-N₄ ring cavities with decreased stability constant to $10^{6.71}$ for reaction $\text{NiA}^{2+} + \text{Ni}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Ni}_2\text{A}^{4+}$. Coordination of additional two cupric ions each in a small cavity of two aza donors (within spherical cavity of the macrocycle), exhibits macrocyclic effect. The enhanced stability (theoretical, but approximate) for reactions $\text{CuA}^{2+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+}$ and $\text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_3\text{A}^{6+}$ over that for open chain ligand 1,3-diaminopropane are $\geq 10^{7.29}$ and $10^{5.55}$, respectively.

Keywords : Nickel(II), copper(II), octaazatricyclo[7.5.5.5^{2,8}]tetracosane, synthesis.

Introduction

A majority of complexes of cyclic ligand have widely been reported¹⁻⁸ to planar tetraaza ring between 12-17 atoms for their structural, spectroscopic, electronic, kinetic and thermodynamic features. The systems consisting of lesser number of donor atoms, studied up to limited extent, are also expected to exhibit similar specificity. Complexes of many cyclic triamines are interesting⁹⁻¹² in which metal ion lies out of the mean plane of the donor atoms and the macrocycle is restricted to facial coordination. X-Ray structural information on $[\text{Cu}(1,4,7\text{-triazacyclododecane})(\text{NO}_3)]\text{NO}_3$ also shows that copper atom is situated away from the plane defined by three donor atoms¹³ but, the coordination geometry about copper atom is irregular and may be described as that of distorted square pyramid or trigonal bipyramid.

The stability constant reported for copper complexes

of 1,4,7-triazacyclononane/decane¹⁴⁻¹⁸ and 1,5,9-triazacycloundecane/dodecane^{14,15,19,20} are very close to that of corresponding open chain ligands 1,4,7-triazaheptane²¹ and 1,5,9-triazanonane¹⁴, respectively. No enhancement in stability of the complexes of these triamines over that of similar open chain ligands is probably due to mismatch between metal and cavity sizes. But, for a matching size system the macrocyclic effect is expected even in case of less than four donor atom macrocycles. Such macrocycles with suitable ring cavity consisting of N₂ or N₃ donors can be achieved by connecting the terminal amine groups of 1,2-diaminoethane, 1,3-diaminopropane, 1,4,7-triazaheptane or 1,5,9-triazanonane with an open organic chain. But, their flexibility, expected highest for lowest number of donor macrocycle, would significantly influence the binding property where the metal atom may lie away from the cavity. But, sterically controlled less flexible such ring

cavities can be provided within spherical cavity of a rigid 3-D macrocycle for suitable fit of metal/solvent coordinated metal ion. The donor groups of such cavities are forced to be closed and shielded from solvation. A large spherical cavity may also accommodate more than one metal ions coordinated to same or different number of donors of the cavity²², and the resulting polymetallic complex may exhibit new properties including the macrocyclic effect. However, the enhanced stability would be affected by electronic and steric forces due to a large connecting group.

Considerable efforts have been made to design macrobicyclic^{3,23-28} and macrotricyclic²⁹⁻³¹ 3-D ligands which form stable complexes of unusual properties with a number of cations. Complexes of many tricyclic cage macrocycles derived from condensation of nickel(II) complexes of planar tetraaza macrocycles [14]-N₄, [12]-N₄ and [10]-N₄ with 1,4,7-triazaheptane³¹ exhibit unique trend of stability. In each cage, nickel(II) ion is octahedrally coordinated to six N-donors. But unlike planar system, their stability increases with decrease in planar cavity size ([14]-N₄ → [10]-N₄). Further, many metalloproteins contain two or more metal centres in close proximity. Thus, it is of considerable interest³²⁻³⁶ to synthesize polymetallic complexes of planar/3-D aza ligands and study their unusual properties to have knowledge on the functioning of the polynuclear sites of metalloproteins.

Earlier we have reported template condensation of many chlorocarbons with linear, di-, tri- or tetramine in presence of nickel(II) or copper(II) leading to metal complexes of tetra^{30,37,38} and polyaza^{39,40} macrocycles including those of macrobicyclic and macrotricyclic (2-D and 3-D) ligands^{3,22,30,31,41-43}. The aim of the present work is to synthesize, study structural properties, spectra and solution behavior of poly-metallic complexes of the tricyclic 3-D macrocycle 3,7,10,14,15,19,20,24-octaazatricyclo[7.5.5.5^{2,8}]tetracosane derived from template condensation of 1,3-diaminopropane with 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane in presence of nickel(II) or copper(II). The reaction scheme is given in Fig. 1. The metal-free macrocycle has also been prepared to investigate thermodynamic properties of the complexes involving coordination through four or less number of donors of different sized ring cavities within spherical cavity of the macrocycle.

In polymetallic complexes, the electron density on non-coordinated groups of the ligand is reduced due to their electron transfer to already coordinated metal. Thus, to understand the true coordination ability of these groups, as in metal-free ligand, the factors responsible for the said electron transfer effect have also been considered. A theoretical value of stability constants of the resulting complex, thus obtained, have been compared with the corresponding value for similar open chain ligand to examine the macrocyclic effect on stability due to two or three aza donor macrocycle. However, the enhanced theoretical value is still expected low as compared to true enhanced stability due to steric factors. For reactions $\text{CuA}^{2+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+}$ and $\text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_3\text{A}^{6+}$ (A = OCTC), where second or third cupric ion is coordinated to only two aza groups, the enhanced theoretical stability over that of corresponding open chain ligand 1,3-diaminopropane are 10^{5.55} and 10^{2.22} respectively. In its support, the similar values have also been calculated from the recently reported data on nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of 2,5,8,10,13,16,17,20,23-nonaazabicyclo[7.7.7]tricosane (NACT)²².

Experimental

Materials :

All solvents, metal salts, amine and chlorocarbon were obtained commercially and were of reagent grade.

Physical and chemical measurements :

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 820 IPC FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr disks. ¹H NMR spectra were obtained with a Bruker DRX 300 (300 MHz FT) spectrophotometer in D₂O solution utilizing DSS as internal standard. The mass spectrum was recorded on a Joel SX 102/DA-600 spectrometer/data system using Argon/Xenon (6 KV, 100 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 KV and the spectrum was recorded at room temperature. *m*-Nitrobenzyl alcohol was used as the matrix. Conductivities were recorded with a DDR conductivity meter (type 304)³⁷. Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were performed at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Ionizable chloride ions were obtained by conductometric titrations. The metal complexes were decomposed as described earlier³⁷ and their metal contents were subsequently determined by EDTA titration⁴⁴.

Fig. 1. Reaction scheme.

Potentiometric titration :

Aqueous mixtures : (i) 0.001046 (N) HNO_3 ; (ii) 0.0005 (M) $\text{OCTC}\cdot 8\text{HCl}$ + (i); (iii) 0.0005 (M) copper nitrate/nickel nitrate + (ii); (iv) 0.001 (M) copper nitrate/nickel nitrate + (ii); (v) 0.0015 (M) copper nitrate + (ii); (vi) 0.002 (M) copper nitrate + (ii) were prepared and titrated against 0.1224 (N) NaOH solution using an EC 5656 pH meter with combined electrode system. The initial volume of each mixture was kept at 50 ml. The data were recorded at 25 °C and at ionic strength of 0.1 (M) KNO_3 . From experimental data, titration curves (pH vs

moles of alkali used per mole of ligand, *a*) were plotted and analyzed^{45,46} to obtain information on metal ligand equilibria in aqueous solution.

Synthesis of nickel(II) complex of OCTC :

Nickel hydroxide (5.00 g, 53.92 mmol) was added to stirred mixture of 1,3-diaminopropane (7.99 g, 107.78 mmol) and 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane (9.05 g, 53.92 mmol) in 200 ml butanol. The resulting mixture, consisting of a thick green precipitate and very light violet solution was then stirred for 5 min. A blue turbid solution with a small quantity of green precipitate was produced which imme-

diately changed to colourless and then to light violet colour. The mixture was then refluxed for 4 h. After being refluxed for about 5 min the mixture changed to blue turbid solution containing a small quantity of the green precipitate. The whole mixture turned into a blue turbid solution after being refluxed for 4 h. It was then cooled, treated with 150 ml of water and aqueous bluish-violet solution containing the product was separated. The negligible amount of green precipitate and the colorless non-aqueous butanol layer were rejected. Concentration and refrigeration of the aqueous solution gave crude, sticky violet crystals of $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The sticky material was removed by treating the product with ether-benzene (1 : 1) mixture on filter paper. The product was recrystallized from water. The resulting crystalline product was further dissolved in methanol and filtered to remove traces of white residue. The pure product was crystallized from the resulting solution. The violet crystalline product was finally washed with ether and dried, yield 10.20 g.

Synthesis of copper(II) complex of OCTC :

The cyclization reaction involving 1,3-diaminopropane (7.60 g, 102.52 mmol), 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane (8.60 g, 51.24 mmol) and copper hydroxide (5.00 g, 51.25 mmol) was carried out by refluxing the mixture in 200 ml butanol. The deep blue mixture changed into a greenish blue solution after continuous heating for 5 h. The greenish blue solution was treated with 120 ml of water and filtered. A small quantity brown residue was rejected. The violet aqueous layer of the filtrate containing the macrocyclic product was separated from the non-aqueous wine-red layer. Concentration and refrigeration of the aqueous layer yielded violet crystalline product of tetrametallic copper(II) complex (unlike nickel(II) system which yielded dimetallic complex) soluble in methanol and water. The product was washed with acetone followed by ether, yield 7.32 g.

Preparation of metal-free macrocycle :

The hydrochloride of the metal-free macrocycle was prepared by the demetallation of the copper(II) or nickel(II) complex. Aqueous solution of the $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3.00 g, 2.65 mmol) was prepared in 100 ml of water. Then the solution was acidified by 15 ml conc.

HCl (12 (N)) with stirring. Removal of copper(II) ion as CuS was achieved by passing H_2S gas into the acidified solution as described earlier⁴⁷. Concentration and crystallization of the solution yielded the metal-free ligand hydrochloride. In nickel(II) system acidified aqueous solution of the complex $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.5 g, 3.28 mmol in 100 ml of water) was concentrated and crystallized. The crystals of the metal-free ligand hydrochloride mixed with green nickel(II) chloride crystals were washed with methanol to obtain pure crystals of the metal-free macrocycle (straw coloured needle shaped crystals, yield 1.58 g). The crystals obtained from both the complexes were finally washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Condensation of 1,3-diaminopropane with 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane in presence of nickel hydroxide yields a mononuclear octahedral nickel(II) complex of the macrocycle 1,4,8,11-tetraaza-2,3,9,10-tetrachlorocyclotetradecane (TTTE). Metal ion is coordinated to four aza donors of the [14]- N_4 planar ring cavity⁴⁸ generated by condensation of two molecules of each 1,3-diaminopropane and 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane. The axial positions are occupied by two H_2O molecules. The reaction proceeds with formation of 1 : 2, nickel-ammine complex. Subsequently, the chlorocarbon condenses with the 50% of the ammine complex leading to formation of $[\text{Ni}(\text{TTTE})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$. Then, remaining amount of the nickel-ammine complex condenses with the resulting product formed at first stage with the generation of the second [14]- N_4 ring. The second nickel(II) ion would also be initially expected in octahedral environment of four aza donors of the second identical ring and two H_2O molecules in axial positions. But, the cavity centres of the two [14]- N_4 rings are at close distance, and therefore, the positively charged metal ions would oppose such coordination. In addition, the spherical cavity of the macrocycle would be crowded by the two H_2O molecules directed towards the spherical cavity centre. Thus, a structural rearrangement would be favoured by coordination of each metal ion in smaller co-facial [12]- N_4 ring cavities (Fig. 1).

The reaction mixture similar to that in nickel(II) system consisting of 1 : 2 : 1, copper hydroxide : 1,3-diaminopropane : 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane unexpectedly yields a tetracopper(II) complex. Mode of condensation leading to formation of this complex shows that 50% of each reactant 1,3-diaminopropane or 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane remains unreacted. The ratio of the reacting molecules copper hydroxide : 1,3-diaminopropane : 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane involved in condensation is 4 : 4 : 2. It has already been reported that condensation of two molecules of each, 1,3-diaminopropane and 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane in presence of two molecules of copper hydroxide yields dicopper(II) complex of TTTE⁴⁹ where, each metal ion is coordinated to two aza donors of the macrocycle. The remaining two positions are occupied by H₂O molecules. In the present system, the dicopper(II) complex of TTE formed by the condensation of 50% blue 1 : 1, copper(II)-ammine complex with 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane further condenses with remaining amount of copper(II)-ammine complex to yield [Cu₄(OCTC)-(H₂O)₈]Cl₈·6H₂O. Here, the ligand encapsulates four copper(II) ions, each coordinated to two aza donors and two water molecules, in its spherical cavity.

The metal complexes and the metal-free ligand were characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, conductivity measurements and infrared, ¹H NMR and mass spectra. The results of elemental analyses, reported in Table 1, indicate the stoichiometry which is in agreement with the formulation given. Evidence for cyclization is demonstrated by the absence of infrared absorption bands that may be attributed to either free or coordinated -NH₂ group^{2,50}. Identical results have been achieved for ligands prepared from nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectrum of [Ni₂(OCTC)(H₂O)₄]Cl₄·5H₂O exhibits no band due to -NH₂ group. A very weak but sharp band attributed to secondary amine at 3150 cm⁻¹ indicates presence of completely condensed macrocyclic organic ligand. The N-H bending mode is seen as a strong but sharp band at 1594 cm⁻¹. A medium but very sharp band at 1065 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν(C-N) vibration. Medium but sharp asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring bands for C-H are seen at 2920, 2870 and 1438 cm⁻¹, respectively. The bands at

1470, 1380, 1328, 1278, 1160, 1100, 1008, 900, 878, 364 and 319 cm⁻¹ are associated with the skeletal vibration of the whole complex. A medium but sharp band at 478 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the nickel-nitrogen bond. Coordination of water is supported by the presence of a very strong but very broad band at 3250 cm⁻¹ followed by a very weak band at 800 cm⁻¹ assigned to stretching and rocking vibrations of the water molecule, respectively. A band at 638 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the ν(Ni-O) vibration of the coordinated water.

In the infrared spectrum of the complex [Cu₄(OCTC)-(H₂O)₈]Cl₈·6H₂O the N-H stretching mode of secondary amine is seen at 3110 cm⁻¹ while the position of the N-H bending mode is at 1580 cm⁻¹. A very weak but very sharp band at 1050 cm⁻¹ is associated with ν(C-N). Coordination of the ligand through the nitrogen is evident by a medium but very sharp band at 488 cm⁻¹. The bands for coordinated water are seen at 3225, 812, 670 and 606 cm⁻¹, and are attributed to ν(O-H), rocking and wagging vibrations of H₂O molecule and ν(Cu-O), respectively.

The OCTC hydrochloride spectrum is different in several respects from the spectrum of its nickel(II) or copper(II) complex. The major difference occurs in 1400–400 cm⁻¹ region where bands due to the water molecules or metal coordinated bonds with nitrogen or oxygen are absent. The ligand hydrochloride exhibits a series of weak but generally sharp bands at 2775, 2644, 2495, 2407, 2366 and 2302 cm⁻¹ and a prominent band at 2019 cm⁻¹ (medium but sharp) associated with >NH₂⁺Cl⁻ groups. Such bands are absent in the metal complexes. The cyclic nature of the metal-free ligand is demonstrated by the similarity of its amine bands with those of the nickel(II) or copper(II) complex. A weak shoulder of the secondary amine appears at 3203 cm⁻¹. The corresponding of δ(N-H) vibration is seen at 1600 cm⁻¹. Strong/medium/weak bands for C-H asymmetric and symmetric stretching and scissoring modes appear at 3008, 2845 and 1402 cm⁻¹, respectively. Bands at 1465, 1338, 1220, 1188, 1033, 941, 770, 620, 419 and 409 cm⁻¹ are also characteristics of the whole ligand molecule. The spectrum of OCTC shows very close correspondence to that of 2,6,8,12,13,17-hexaazabicyclo[5.5.5]heptadecane (HBCH), reported earlier²², in the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ region probably due to close structural similarity.

Comparison with related systems :

The $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ for $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex is comparable to that previously reported²² for $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{HBCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_6$ (492 cm^{-1}) complex. But, $\nu(\text{Cu-O})$ for coordinated water in OCTC system is at higher frequency (606 cm^{-1}) due to their suitable fit in the larger cavity than that in HBCH system (590 cm^{-1}) of smaller cavity. Spherical cavity of NACT described earlier²⁸, is further more suitable to encapsulate three copper(II) ions as well as three coordinated water molecules as indicated by $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu-O})$ at higher frequencies 522 and 629 cm^{-1} , respectively. Coordination of three nickel(II) ions, each to four aza donors in the planar $[12]\text{-N}_4$ cavities of tricyclic macrocycles 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[20.10.0.0^{6,17}]dotriacontane (DOCD) or 2,5,8,11,13,16,19,22,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[10.10.10.0]dotriacontane (DTCD) has been studied^{41,51}. The axial coordination positions in these systems are occupied by water molecules. The $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ at low frequency in OCTC complex as compared to that in DOCD (525 cm^{-1}) and DTCD (500 cm^{-1}) complexes, is expected in view of a smaller non-planar $[12]\text{-N}_4$ ring cavity of OCTC. But, the $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ for coordinated water in OCTC complex at higher frequency (638 cm^{-1}) than that in the complex of DOCD (629 cm^{-1}) or DTCD (570 cm^{-1}) may be believed due to low electron density do-

nated by aza donors to nickel(II) in OCTC complex. In addition, two water molecules in OCTC complex are encapsulated within spherical cavity.

¹H NMR spectrum :

The spectrum of OCTC hydrochloride shows broad triplet and pentet ascribed to α - and β -methylene protons centred at 3.16 and 2.01 ppm, respectively. Their positions of resonances are in agreement with the integration of the signals (proton ratio 16 : 8). The NH_2^+ proton resonance is centred at 5.00 ppm. The CH proton resonance is probably obscured by the NH_2^+ protons. In the nickel complex very complex multiplets are seen in the region 3.09–1.57 ppm. A broad peak observed in the region 5.12–4.38 ppm is expected for the coordinated water and NH group.

Mass spectrum :

The FAB spectrum of $\text{OCTC} \cdot 8\text{HCl}$ has been useful in completing its characterization. Intensity of the highest mass peak close to molecular ion at m/z 624 is very weak and comparable to those of earlier reported aza macrocycles^{37,49}. The low m/z value is associated with the H lost due to fragmentation. A series of fragment ion involving loss of H/HCl and NH, CH_2 , CH_2CH_2 , $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$, CH or CH.CH groups from different positions of the macrocycle hydrochloride (Fig. 1) are seen in the mass spectrum (Fig. 2). The characteristic pattern

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum (FABMS) of $\text{OCTC} \cdot 8\text{HCl}$.

of fragmentation and the m/z values of the ions are given in Fig. 3.

The medium intensity peak at m/z 273 appears for a stable planar [14]-N₄ ring. Isotopic peaks due to HCl molecules in many ions also are in support of the fragment ions. Four isotopic peaks, two for each ion [CHNHCH₂CH₂CH₂·HCl]⁺ (m/z 106, 108), [CHNHCH₂CH₂CH₂·HCl+H]⁺ (m/z 107, 109) and [NHCH₂CH₂CH₂NH·HCl]⁺ (m/z 108, 110) are seen in the spectrum. The highest peak (base peak) may be regarded as a combination of the common peaks at m/z

108. Similarly 8 peaks (m/z 119–126, with highest peak at m/z 120) are expected for the fragments [CHCHNHCH₂CH₂CH₂·HCl]⁺ (m/z 119, 121), [CHCHNHCH₂CH₂CH₂·HCl]⁺ (m/z 120, 122), [CHNHCH₂CH₂CH₂NH·HCl]⁺ (m/z 121, 123), [CHNHCH₂CH₂CH₂NH·HCl-H]⁺ (m/z 120, 122), [CHNHCH₂CH₂CH₂NH·HCl + 3H]⁺ (m/z 124, 126), [CHCHNHCH₂CH₂CH₂NH·HCl+2H]⁺ (m/z 123, 125).

Solubility, conductivity and other data :

The metal complexes and the metal-free ligand hydrochloride are highly soluble in water and less soluble in

Fig. 3. Fragmentation pattern of OCTC·8HCl.

other polar solvents like methanol, ethanol, DMF, DMSO, etc. The molar conductivity and the percentage of ionizable chloride ions for the complexes recorded in Table 1 are in support of their ionic structures. The molar conductance values of 498 and 886 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ are consistent with 4 : 1 and 8 : 1 electrolytes for $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, respectively. The nickel complex of OCTC has low decomposition point, whereas its copper complex is thermally more stable and decomposes near its melting point. The metal-free ligand OCTC·8HCl decomposes at 226 °C. The metal complexes were heated to 120 °C to remove their water of crystallization. The loss in mass is equivalent to water of crystallization.

Solution stability :

Copper(II) system : Dissociation of eight protons from the colourless ligand hydrochloride is indicated by the corresponding titration curve (Fig. 4). The light greenish-blue titration mixture of 1 : 1, Cu^{2+} -macrocycle gradually turns violet in the range of pH 6.4–8.0. The violet colour intensity further increases up to pH 11.2.

complexes.

A gradual colour change from greenish-blue to blue due to formation of blue copper(II) complex $\text{Cu}_2\text{H}_2\text{A}^{6+}$ is seen in 2 : 1, Cu^{2+} -ligand mixture up to pH ~ 7.5 ($a = 6.0$), where the second cupric ion is coordinated to only two aza donors of the macrocycle. The colour intensity of the mixture further increases between pH 7.5 and 10.5. At pH ~ 10.5 there is steep inflection ($a \sim 10.0$) in the titration curve. Thus, deprotonation of $\text{Cu}_2\text{H}_2\text{A}^{6+}$ leading to formation of $\text{Cu}_2\text{HA}^{5+}$ and Cu_2A^{4+} in the range of pH 7.5–7.9, and finally, association of two OH^- ions with the second cupric ion between pH 7.9 and 10.5 are expected.

In 3 : 1, Cu^{2+} -macrocycle system formation of a trimetallic light blue complex Cu_3A^{6+} is expected from the observed colour change (greenish-blue to light blue) between $a = 6.0$ and 8.0 (between pH 6.0 and 7.5), where, third cupric ion is coordinated to last two aza donors of the macrocycle. Between pH 7.5 and 8.2 ($a = 10.0$), further colour change from light blue to deep blue indicates association of two OH^- ions to ligand coordi-

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the macrocyclic compounds

Compd.	Colour (colour at D.P.)	Yield (%) (m.p. °C)	Λ_M (Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	% Found (Calcd.)				
				C	H	N	Cu/Ni	Cl ^c
$[\text{Cu}_4(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Violet	50.5	498	17.06	5.70	9.98	22.54	25.00
$\text{Cu}_4\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{64}\text{N}_8\text{O}_{14}\text{Cl}_8$	(Brown liquid) ^b	(185) ^d		(17.00)	(5.72)	(9.91)	(22.48)	(25.08)
$[\text{Ni}_2(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Violet	49.7	886	25.29	7.14	14.75	15.46	18.56
$\text{Ni}_2\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{54}\text{N}_8\text{O}_9\text{Cl}_4$	(Bluish-violet)	(122) ^d		(25.22)	(7.16)	(14.71)	(15.41)	(18.61)
OCTC·8HCl	Straw colour	76.3 ^a	–	30.47	7.06	17.78	–	44.72
$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_8 \cdot 8\text{HCl}$	(–)	(226) ^d		(30.39)	(7.03)	(17.73)	(–)	(44.86)

^aYield is based on nickel complex; ^bbrownish-black at 258 °C; ^cionizable chloride ion; ^ddecomposition point.

The corresponding titration curve showing a steep inflection near pH ~ 8.0 ($a \sim 4.0$) indicates formation of $\text{CuH}_4\text{A}^{6+}$ involving coordination of cupric ion to four aza donors in a tetra aza cavity of the macrocycle. Again, there are two very weak inflections at $a = 5$ and 6.0 in the titration curve, which indicate dissociation of two protons in different steps. Between $a = 6.0$ and 8.0 two equilibria corresponding to dissociation of last two protons from $\text{CuH}_2\text{A}^{4+}$, coexist resulting the formation of mono-protonated CuHA^{3+} and non-protonated CuA^{2+}

nated cupric ion to form deep blue hydroxo complexes $\text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})^{5+}$ and $\text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})_2^{4+}$. Beyond pH 8.2, there is no colour/intensity change, but, the corresponding titration curve shows an increase in a value followed by a steep inflection at pH ~ 10.2 ($a = 12.0$). It indicates association of additional two OH^- ions with $\text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})_2^{4+}$ resulting the formation of $\text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})_3^{3+}$ and $\text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})_4^{2+}$. The 4 : 1, metal-ligand mixture shows colour changes almost similar to those in corresponding 3 : 1 system. In addition, light blue turbidity appears at

Fig. 4. pH vs a curves : (1) OCTC·8HCl, (2) Ni²⁺-OCTC·8HCl, (3) 2Ni²⁺-OCTC·8HCl, (4) Cu²⁺-OCTC·8HCl, (5) 2 Cu²⁺-OCTC·8HCl, (6) 3Cu⁺-OTCE·8HCl, (7) 4Cu⁺-OTCE·8HCl (OCTC·8HCl = 0.0005 M).

pH ~ 7.4 due to hydrolysis of the fourth cupric ion. The corresponding titration curve, as expected, shows steep inflection at $a = 14.0$.

In the complex CuH₄A⁶⁺, cupric ion coordinated to four aza donors, may be accommodated in a cavity of one of the four [14]-N₄ rings consisting of (3,7,10,14), (15,19,20,24), (3,7,15,19) and (10,14,20,24) aza donors. These nonplanar rings are fused along two CH-CH bonds. Among them (3,7,15,19) or (10,14,20,24) donor ring is more planar than the remaining two. At first appearance, coordination of copper to (3,7,15,19) or (10,14,20,24) donors in the corresponding cavity (where the two cavity centres coincide) seems to be preferred due to its structure (near to planar). But insertion of the metal ion in the ring cavity is expected to be opposed on account of steric hindrance by the -NHCH₂CH₂CH₂NH- group of the metal approaching side. In addition, the whole size of the (3,7,15,19) or (15,19,20,24) donor ring, through which the metal approaches to the cavity centre, is much reduced as compared to that for the similar [14]-N₄ planar

cyclam structure. Subsequently, the metal ion is held in the (3,7,10,14) aza donor cavity through four coordinate bonds. Since, the ring is nonplanar and metal is above the four aza plane in the direction away from the spherical cavity centre of macrocycle, the four sp³-hybridized orbitals one from each donor consisting of lone pair of electrons would partially overlap with the appropriate metal orbital leading to incomplete lone pair donation to metal. Therefore, stability constant (10^{17.78}) is low as compared to that for corresponding reaction for cyclam³⁶ ($K = 10^{27}$). For a similar reaction of 3-D ligand 2,6,8,12,13,17-hexaazadicyclo[5.5.5]heptadecane (HBCH) involving copper coordination to four donors of nonplanar [12]-N₄ ring cavity, reported recently²², the stability is reduced to 10^{15.41}.

Initially, it was considered that second cupric ion in dicupric complex must be accommodated in the identical cavity of (15,19,20,24) donors. But, an observation on blue colour change below pH 7.5 (or below $a \sim 6.0$) in 2 : 1, metal-ligand mixture, it is concluded that second

copper ion, in a tetra coordinate environment in blue complex $\text{Cu}_2\text{H}_2\text{A}^{6+}$, $\text{Cu}_2\text{HA}^{5+}$, Cu_2A^{4+} , $\text{Cu}_2\text{A}(\text{OH})^{3+}$ or $\text{Cu}_2\text{A}(\text{OH})_2^{2+}$ is coordinated to only two aza donors (15,19) or (20,24) of the macrocycle and two oxygen ($\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{OH}^-$) donors in aqueous solution. It may also be added that the cavity centers of the (3,7,10,14) and (15,19,20,24) donors are at short distance from each other and therefore, the first coordinated Cu^{2+} ion of (3,7,10,14) donor cavity would oppose coordination of the second positively charged cupric ion in the (15,19,20,24) donor cavity. For reaction $\text{CuA}^{2+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+}$, the stability constant ($K_4 = K_3 \cdot K_1^{\text{H}''} \cdot K_2^{\text{H}''} / K_1^{\text{H}'} \cdot K_2^{\text{H}'} \cdot K_3^{\text{H}'} \cdot K_4^{\text{H}'}$) is exceptionally about 10^2 times high as compared to $10^{9.82}$ reported⁵² for $\text{Cu}^{2+} + 1,3\text{-diaminopropane} \rightleftharpoons [\text{Cu}(1,3\text{-diaminopropane})]^{2+}$. The second cupric ion and (15) $\text{NH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{NH}$ (19) are expected in a single plane where, lone pair of electron containing hybridized orbitals of donors (15) and (19) completely overlap with the metal orbitals.

The enhanced stability experimentally obtained (above) cannot be theoretically considered true for interaction of donors (15) and (19) with second cupric ion due to some electron density transfer from these donors towards already coordinated first cupric ion as indicated by lowering of the corresponding titration curve from that of the ligand between $a = 4$ and 8. Theoretically, true coordination ability of donors (15) and (19) as in absence of the first cupric ion, can be obtained by replacement of the related factors $K_1^{\text{H}'}$ and $K_2^{\text{H}'}$, responsible for electron density transfer towards first cupric ion, by K_5^{H} and K_6^{H} , respectively. Thus modified K_4 value is reported in Table 2. The enhanced stability ($10^{5.55}$) over that for 1,3-diaminopropane is expected due to suitable fit of the water coordinated metal in the cavity.

Again, the very low value of the stability constant $K_6 = K_5 / K_1^{\text{H}''} \cdot K_2^{\text{H}''}$ ($10^{5.56}$) for $\text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_3\text{A}^{6+}$ as compared to $10^{11.73}$ for $\text{CuA}^{2+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+}$ is due to high electron density transfer from donors (20,24) to first and second cupric ion. The value was theoretically modified similar to the previous system by replacing electron withdrawing factors $K_1^{\text{H}''}$ and $K_2^{\text{H}''}$ by K_7^{H} and K_8^{H} , respectively. The modified theoretical K_6 value ($10^{12.04}$) indicating macrocyclic effect is too low as compared to modified K_4 value ($10^{15.37}$) probably due to

crowding of the spherical cavity by four H_2O molecules, and increased steric effects. To minimize this crowding, the two H_2O molecules coordinated to the third cupric ion are favourably replaced by two OH^- ions as indicated by high equilibrium constants $10^{6.35}$ and $10^{6.04}$ (Table 2). The two lower values $10^{5.66}$ and $10^{4.30}$ correspond to association of OH^- ions to second cupric ion in tricupric complex, which is confirmed by similarity of these values with $10^{5.20}$ and $10^{4.45}$ reported for OH^- ion association to second cupric ion in dicupric complex.

In copper(II)-NACT system, the third cupric ion is coordinated to three aza donors. The modified theoretical stability constants $K_6 = K_3 / K_8^{\text{H}} \cdot K_9^{\text{H}}$ (Table 2) calculated for corresponding reaction is enhanced by $10^{2.47}$ times over $10^{16.02}$ reported for the $\text{Cu}^{2+} + 1,4,7\text{-triazheptane} \rightleftharpoons [\text{Cu}(1,4,7\text{-triazheptane})]^{2+}$ reaction⁵³. The enhancement may be regarded due to suitable fit of metal in the cavity. A low enhancement in the value is due to crowding of the spherical cavity by three H_2O molecules coordinated to metal ions. To reduce the crowding strain by H_2O molecules, formation of hydroxo complexes is highly favoured as indicated by corresponding constants²². In a polymetallic complex of 3-D macrocycle, for metal coordination to two or three aza donors, the enhanced theoretical stability constant calculated as above may still be influenced by steric factors attributed to large connecting group. Therefore, it may be considered approximate (low) but, very close to true value in a complex of small macrocycle. However, the enhanced stability due to two or three aza donors for the cupric complex of OCTC or NACT is in agreement with that reported^{6,36} for similar complexes of other tetra aza planar macrocycles.

Nickel(II) system: The 1 : 1 or 2 : 1, Ni^{2+} -OCTC·8HCl mixture appears colourless in the entire pH-range. But, in 3 : 1, Ni^{2+} -ligand system a light green turbidity formation occurs from pH ~ 9.0 as a result of hydrolysis of excess of Ni^{2+} ion. Formation of nickel(II) complex $\text{NiH}_4\text{A}^{6+}$ is evident from the titration curve of 1 : 1, metal-macrocycle system, which shows an inflection at $a = 4$ (pH ~ 9.2). In this tetra-protonated complex Ni^{2+} ion is expected to coordinate four aza donors. Further, beyond pH ~ 9.2 four equilibria (Table 2) corresponding to proton dissociation occur between $a = 4$ and 8. The pH vs a curve for 2 : 1, Ni^{2+} -ligand mixture shows two

inflections – first very weak at $a = 4$ (pH ~ 8.8) and second very steep at $a = 8.0$ (pH ~ 10.5) indicating formation of a non-protonated (Ni_2A^{4+}) complex, in addition to the tetra-protonated complex. The second Ni^{2+} ion is also held in a cavity of four aza donors. The equilibrium constants obtained from the analysis of the related titration curves are reported in Table 2.

Like cupric system, Ni^{2+} ion is considered to coordinate (3,7,10,14) aza donors of the [14]- N_4 ring. But, then second nickel(II) ion cannot coordinate to remaining (15,19,20,24) aza donors with the similar reason as discussed in copper(II) system. Further, as Ni^{2+} ion prefers octahedral geometry, the axial positions in $\text{NiH}_4\text{A}^{6+}$,

Table 2. Equilibrium constants for nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of OCTC (A) at 25 °C ($\mu = 0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$)

Reaction	log k^b	
$\text{H}_8\text{A}^{8+} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_7\text{A}^{7+} + \text{H}^+$	-8.18	K_1^{H}
$\text{H}_7\text{A}^{7+} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_6\text{A}^{6+} + \text{H}^+$	-8.92	K_2^{H}
$\text{H}_6\text{A}^{6+} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_5\text{A}^{5+} + \text{H}^+$	-9.40	K_3^{H}
$\text{H}_5\text{A}^{5+} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_4\text{A}^{4+} + \text{H}^+$	-9.84	K_4^{H}
$\text{H}_4\text{A}^{4+} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_3\text{A}^{3+} + \text{H}^+$	-10.30	K_5^{H}
$\text{H}_3\text{A}^{3+} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{A}^{2+} + \text{H}^+$	-10.80	K_6^{H}
$\text{H}_2\text{A}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{HA}^+ + \text{H}^+$	-11.02	K_7^{H}
$\text{HA}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{A} + \text{H}^+$	-11.40	K_8^{H}
$\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{H}_4\text{A}^{4+} \rightleftharpoons \text{NiH}_4\text{A}^{6+}$	6.77	K_1
$\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{NiA}^{2+}$	9.28	K_2
$\text{NiH}_4\text{A}^{6+} \rightleftharpoons \text{NiH}_3\text{A}^{5+} + \text{H}^+$	-9.52	$K_1^{\text{H}'}$
$\text{NiH}_3\text{A}^{5+} \rightleftharpoons \text{NiH}_2\text{A}^{4+} + \text{H}^+$	-9.94	$K_2^{\text{H}'}$
$\text{NiH}_2\text{A}^{4+} \rightleftharpoons \text{NiHA}^{3+} + \text{H}^+$	-10.55	$K_3^{\text{H}'}$
$\text{NiHA}^{3+} \rightleftharpoons \text{NiA}^{2+} + \text{H}^+$	-11.00	$K_4^{\text{H}'}$
$\text{NiH}_3\text{A}^{5+} + \text{Ni}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Ni}_2\text{A}^{4+} + 3\text{H}^+$	-16.47 ^a	K_3
$\text{NiA}^{2+} + \text{Ni}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Ni}_2\text{A}^{4+}$	6.71 10.91 ^a (15.86) ^a	K_4
$\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{H}_4\text{A}^{4+} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuH}_4\text{A}^{6+}$	12.40	K_1
$\text{CuH}_4\text{A}^{6+} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuH}_3\text{A}^{5+} + \text{H}^+$	-8.36	$K_1^{\text{H}'}$
$\text{CuH}_3\text{A}^{5+} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuH}_2\text{A}^{4+} + \text{H}^+$	-9.10	$K_2^{\text{H}'}$
$\text{CuH}_2\text{A}^{4+} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuHA}^{3+} + \text{H}^+$	-9.98	$K_3^{\text{H}'}$
$\text{CuHA}^{3+} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuA}^{2+} + \text{H}^+$	-10.70	$K_4^{\text{H}'}$
$\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuA}^{2+}$	17.78	K_2
$\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{CuH}_2\text{A}^{4+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{H}_2\text{A}^{6+}$	6.99	K_3'
$\text{Cu}_2\text{H}_2\text{A}^{6+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{HA}^{5+} + \text{H}^+$	-7.76	$K_1^{\text{H}''}$
$\text{Cu}_2\text{HA}^{5+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+} + \text{H}^+$	-8.18	$K_2^{\text{H}''}$

Table-2 (contd.)

$\text{Cu}_2\text{H}_4\text{A}^{6+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{H}_2\text{A}^{6+} + 2\text{H}^+$	-10.47 -3.88 ^a	K_3
$\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{CuA}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+}$	11.73 (15.55)	K_4
$\text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{A}(\text{OH})^{3+}$	5.20	K_7
$\text{Cu}_2\text{A}(\text{OH})^{3+} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{A}(\text{OH})_2^{2+}$	4.45	K_8
$\text{Cu}_2\text{H}_2\text{A}^{6+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_3\text{A}^{6+} + 2\text{H}^+$	-10.38 -3.58 ^a	K_5
$\text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_3\text{A}^{6+}$	5.56 (12.04) 14.32 ^a (18.49) ^a	K_6
$\text{Cu}_3\text{A}^{6+} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})^{5+}$	6.35	K_9
$\text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})^{5+} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})_2^{4+}$	6.04	K_{10}
$\text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})_2^{4+} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})_3^{3+}$	5.66	K_{11}
$\text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})_3^{3+} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_3\text{A}(\text{OH})_4^{2+}$	4.30	K_{12}

() Theoretically modified values : considering no electron transfer; ^aNACT system²², ^bvalues are $\pm 0.02-0.26$.

$\text{NiH}_3\text{A}^{5+}$, $\text{NiH}_2\text{A}^{4+}$, NiHA^{3+} or NiA^{2+} may be occupied by water molecules, and if a dimetallic complex is formed accommodating two Ni^{2+} ion. In the said cavities of (3,7,10,14) and (15,19,20,24) donors, the steric clashes between two axial molecules directed towards the spherical cavity centre will oppose such metal-ligand coordination. However, these steric forces can be removed in a square-pyramidal structure, but repulsion between the two nickel(II) ions as described in copper(II) system would again oppose accommodation of second nickel(II) ion in (15,19,20,24) donor cavity. Thus, in Ni_2A^{4+} structural rearrangement is expected by coordination of Ni^{2+} ions in smaller [12]- N_4 ring cavities of (3,7,20,24) and (10,14,15,19) donors. Equilibrium constant ($K_4 = 10^{6.71}$) for reaction $\text{NiA}^{2+} + \text{Ni}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Ni}_2\text{A}^{4+}$ is also comparable to that ($10^{6.93}$) for reaction $\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{HBCH} = [\text{Ni}(\text{HBCH})]^{2+}$ (where Ni^{2+} coordinates to identical [12]- N_4 ring cavity)²². A higher value ($K_2 = 10^{9.28}$) for reaction $\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{NiA}^{2+}$ is further in support of first nickel(II) ion coordination to (3,7,10,14) donors in absence of second nickel(II) ion. Thus, it is concluded that in solution the single Ni^{2+} ion enters into the (3,7,10,14) donor [14]- N_4 ring cavity. But, in presence of two nickel(II) ions there is structural rearrangement in coordination position leading to accommodation of each metal in smaller ring [12]- N_4 cavity.

Spherical cavity of NACT accommodates only two

Ni^{2+} ions (first and second coordinated to six and three aza donors, respectively, each in octahedral environment)²² unlike its copper(II) system where a trimetallic complex Cu_3A^{6+} is formed involving coordination of each cupric ion to three aza donors. The modified theoretical stability constant ($10^{15.86}$) for reaction $\text{NiA}^{2+} + \text{Ni}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{NiA}^{4+}$ (using the relation $K_4 = K_3/K_7^{\text{H}}K_8^{\text{H}}K_9^{\text{H}}$) is high as compared to $10^{10.89}$ reported⁵⁴ for reaction $\text{Ni}^{2+} + 1,4,7\text{-triazapeptane} \rightleftharpoons [\text{Ni}(1,4,7\text{-triazapeptane})]^{2+}$. The enhanced stability ($10^{4.97}$) due to macrocyclic effect is low as compared to 10^7 reported for Ni^{2+} -cyclam system by Hinze and Margerum⁵⁵ probably due to mismatch between the sizes of the vacant spherical cavity (vacant after accommodation of the first nickel(II) ion), and the H_2O coordinated second nickel(II) ion, and steric effect of the large group connecting the terminal amines of 1,4,7-triazapeptane. Further, unlike copper system under the experimental pH condition no replacement of H_2O by OH^- ion also indicates loose fit of solvent coordinated metal.

Conclusion

Cyclization reaction involving 1 : 2 : 1, metal (nickel(II) or copper(II)) : 1,3-diaminopropane : 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane in *n*-butanol yielded structurally different complexes $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{OCTC})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ of the 3-D ligand 3,7,10,14,15,19,20,24-octazacyclo[7.5.5.5^{2,8}]tetracosane (OCTC). The thermodynamic stability constant $10^{15.37}$ (theoretical values) for the reaction $\text{CuA}^{2+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+}$ involving coordination of ligand OCTC to second cupric ion, through 2 aza donors, is high as compared to $10^{9.82}$ for $\text{Cu}^{2+} + 1,3\text{-diaminopropane} \rightleftharpoons [\text{Cu}(1,3\text{-diaminopropane})]^{2+}$. Similarly, in dinickel(II) complex of NACT the second nickel(II) ion is also coordinated to only 3 aza donors and the complex exhibits enhanced stability ($10^{4.97}$) for the reaction $\text{NiA}^{2+} + \text{Ni}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Ni}_2\text{A}^{4+}$ over that for 1,4,7-triazapeptane ($10^{10.89}$). The enhanced stabilities in these two systems are in agreement with those reported for tetraaza donor macrocycles. Again, the enhanced stabilities $10^{2.22}$ and $10^{2.47}$ of the tricupric complexes of OCTC and NACT for reaction $\text{Cu}_2\text{A}^{4+} + \text{Cu}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_3\text{A}^{6+}$ over those of corresponding open chain ligands are comparable, while the third cupric ion in Cu_3A^{6+} are coordi-

nated to two and three donors. Here, the low enhancement in stability may be expected due to poor fitting of the metal ion in the cavity and steric clashes among coordinated H_2O molecules. Thus, it may be suggested that enhanced stability is independent of the number of coordinated donor atoms of XY plane, and is expected maximum for an ideal fit of the metal in absence of any steric interaction attributed to metal coordinated solvent. However, a definite conclusion for a relation between number of donor atoms and the macrocyclic effect on stability can be drawn by studying more simple and polymetallic complex systems.

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